

How the Global AI Race Shapes the Gulf's Hedging Strategy?

Yasir Atalan

Yasir Atalan is deputy director in the Futures Lab at the Center for Strategic and International Studies as well as faculty fellow at the Center for Data Science at American University. His research focuses on technology and international security, with particular emphasis on how artificial intelligence is reshaping conflict dynamics.

The global AI race is increasingly defining international politics because states now compete over the infrastructure that makes advanced AI possible. While algorithms and model architectures diffuse through research and markets, compute (high-end chips, hyperscale data centers, and cloud platforms) remains concentrated, expensive, and politically controllable, which makes it a strategic bottleneck. Control over compute has therefore become a tool of competition, with the US-China rivalry leveraging it through export controls, licensing, and platform governance. Gulf states such as the UAE, Saudi Arabia, and Qatar occupy a key position in this emerging order because they are deploying sovereign wealth and energy advantages to position themselves as regional AI hubs, even as they remain embedded in US security architectures and deepen economic engagement with China. Their AI investments, therefore, cannot be understood as purely developmental or economic diversification strategies. As AI supply chains become securitized, these infrastructure choices are increasingly embedded in alliance politics, exposing Gulf states to compliance demands and alignment pressures. In this intervention, I examine how the global AI race narrows and reshapes Gulf hedging options under these evolving constraints.

Why Compute Matters for the AI Race?

To understand why Gulf AI strategies are increasingly entangled in alliance politics, it is first necessary to clarify why compute has become the decisive resource in the global AI race. Among algorithms, data, and compute, which are three components of advanced AI (Buchanan 2020), compute has a unique character. It has a rivalrous and binding constraint because advanced AI training and large-scale inference depend on scarce physical systems and reliable compute power rather than code alone. Scaling-law research shows that AI model performance tends to improve in predictable ways as training compute increases (Kaplan et al. 2020). This is why a competitive AI stack requires advanced chips, hyperscale cloud and data center capacity, orchestration software, specialized engineering talent, and continuous electricity and cooling – all of which must operate together to produce competitive performance (OECD 2023; Scharre 2024). Even when open models lower entry barriers, infrastructure concentration and capital intensity continue to limit who can compete in advanced AI systems (OECD 2023; Scharre 2024). In this sense, compute functions as the binding constraint that structures competition in the AI era.

This technological dependence matters politically because compute is not only decisive for advanced AI but also excludable. Contrary to data and algorithm, compute's excludable and measurable nature makes it governable, turning it into a strategic instrument rather than a neutral market commodity (Sastry et al. 2024; Scharre 2024). States and firms can deny access to compute through ownership, export licensing, cloud account controls, and compliance systems embedded in provider operations (Sastry et al. 2024). Crucially, these restrictions are enforceable because compute can be counted and tracked in ways that data and algorithms often cannot. Governments and cloud providers can set benchmarks for how much computing power is being used, monitor the size of the chip clusters involved, and rely on provider records that show who is accessing large-scale compute and when. (Shavit, 2023; Vaynman, 2021). This combination of denial and traceability transforms compute from a technical input into a strategic asset capable of structuring international alignments and shaping geopolitical bargaining.

US-China Competition and Politics of Alignment

Given the nature of compute, the US-China AI rivalry appears less as a race over model quality and more as a contest over control of compute chokepoints within the AI stack. Advantages in chips, fabrication equipment, cloud architecture, and data-center capacity generate cumulative geopolitical spillovers in productivity, military capability, and rule-setting power (Ding and Dafoe 2021). This is why both the US and China sought to reduce

dependence on each other's supply chains in the AI ecosystem. This logic underpins US export controls, which target advanced semiconductors and manufacturing bottlenecks in order to transform infrastructure dependence into strategic leverage.¹ Yet this strategy is debated. Broad denial may protect security but risks accelerating substitution and alienating third states, including US partners, from frontier access. By contrast, selective conditional access through US-governed cloud platforms can preserve influence, sustain ecosystem dependence, and facilitate coalition building under monitoring regimes (Sastry et al. 2024).

If this debate intensifies, further securitization of AI supply chains is likely. This dynamic aligns with weaponized interdependence, where technological hub states convert network centrality into coercive power (Farrell and Newman 2019). With jurisdiction over critical nodes, a state can impose a chokepoint effect by denying advanced chips or cloud capacity (Farrell and Newman 2019). Over time, sustained restriction and compliance pressure can push the system toward bifurcation, hardening rival ecosystems and narrowing strategic flexibility (Woods 2025). Crucially, this trajectory is reinforced by the dual-use character of compute. When technologies serve both civilian and military purposes, states face acute information asymmetries about intent and usage, which increases incentives to design institutions that reduce uncertainty through monitoring and verification (Vaynman and Volpe, 2023). This is why the US and China could embed verification into access to compute through monitoring and reporting requirements that further

¹ Bureau of Industry and Security (BIS), "Additional Export Controls: Advanced Computing and Semiconductor Manufacturing Items," Federal Register 87(197), October 13, 2022, 62186–62215 (2022-21658); BIS, "Additional Export Controls: Advanced Computing Items—Updates and Corrections," Federal Register 88(205), October 25, 2023, 73458–73517 (2023-23055); BIS, "Changes to EAR Controls for Advanced Computing Items and Supercomputers," Federal Register 89(234), December 5, 2024 (2024-28270).

securitize the supply chain. In the end, technological change steadily compresses hedging options for the GCC states (Lehdonvirta, Wu, and Hawkins 2025).

Gulf's AI Ambitions

These structural pressures become particularly visible in the Gulf where countries such as Saudi Arabia and the UAE have accelerated AI infrastructure investment by leveraging sovereign wealth funds and energy advantages to position themselves as regional compute hubs. In Saudi Arabia, Mohammed Bin Salman's Vision 2030 and Neom, Saudi Arabia's flagship smart-city and industrial megaproject, frame AI infrastructure as part of a broader political economy transformation that seeks to convert hydrocarbon wealth into long-term technological competitiveness and reshape domestic rentier relations (Hassan 2020; Herb and Lynch 2019; Hameed 2020). For these countries' AI ambitions, abundant and relatively stable energy supplies play a significant role because large-scale AI training and inference are power-intensive, making electricity availability and cooling capacity central determinants of where frontier compute can be located (Soliman 2025). In line with this, recent announcements indicate a sharp expansion in planned capacity, including Stargate UAE's initial 200 MW phase expected in 2026 with eventual multi-gigawatt ambitions, Saudi Arabia's forthcoming AWS region backed by multi-billion-dollar investment, and Qatar's reported 20-billion-dollar AI infrastructure partnership through Qai. This acceleration is also reflected in Figure 1, where planned installations place the UAE and Saudi Arabia among the top global locations in H100-equivalent

capacity, which is widely treated as a benchmark "frontier" compute accelerator for training and running large AI models (Pliz et al., 2025).

Initially, the Gulf investments were embedded in a portfolio strategy that balanced engagement with both US-led and China-linked cloud ecosystems (Chaziza 2024; Bakir and Al-Shamari 2025). This approach was visible early in the region's cloud architecture, including Alibaba Cloud's Dubai launch in 2016 and AWS's first Middle East region in Bahrain in 2019, alongside continuing openness to Chinese vendors such as Huawei Cloud's Riyadh region in 2023. But as frontier compute for AI becomes securitized, access to the US AI stack increasingly travels with governance conditions, including security assurances, audit requirements, and restrictions on technology transfer, as illustrated by the framing of Microsoft's investment in G42 around intergovernmental compliance commitments (Soliman, 2026).²

What Are the Hedging Options for Gulf States?

The future of compute will shape alliance dynamics in the Gulf because the practical space for hedging depends on how far the United States and China push exclusion through network chokepoints and how strictly those rules are enforced across supply chains and platforms (Farrell and Newman 2019). As long as access to frontier chips, cloud services, and governance frameworks remains mediated through US-centered chokepoints, Gulf states will find that the highest-value AI compute infrastructure is increasingly tied to compliance regimes and security assurances, which narrows the scope

² Reporting of the deal suggested that any approval of AI chips sale is subject to Department of Commerce. See: <https://www.reuters.com/world/middle-east/microsofts-uae-deal-could-transfer-key-us-chips-ai-technology-abroad-2024-05-23/>

for unconstrained dual alignment (Farrell and Newman 2019). Washington already has some digital-security campaigns, such as efforts to exclude Huawei from 5G ecosystems and Clean Network, an initiative aimed at excluding Chinese telecom and digital infrastructure vendors from its networks. The options for the Gulf states become narrower if Washington broadens these existing digital-security campaigns into the AI domain by treating data centers, cloud access, and model training as alliance-sensitive infrastructure (Chaziza, 2024). More recently, Pax Silica, an initiative on securing critical supply chain security signed also by Qatar and UAE, is a signal in this direction by Washington to institutionalize security screening around AI infrastructure. Under those conditions, Gulf governments would face stronger pressure to protect critical AI systems from Chinese vendors and to adopt procurement, standards,

and auditing practices that demonstrate ecosystem separation (Chaziza 2024). This dependence dynamic could also deepen further if Gulf countries seek broader security cooperation with the US to protect data centers against physical and cyberattacks in an increasingly volatile region.

On the other hand, other mediating factors could play a role in shaping supply chain securitization. Great power economic statecraft is mediated by firms that own key parts of the compute stack, which can preserve limited space for Gulf states to maneuver even under intensifying rivalry (Chen and Evers 2023). As hyperscalers, chipmakers, and data-center operators bear the commercial and technical costs of compliance, they have incentives to lobby for narrower controls, clearer rules, and workable verification regimes. Because maximalist restrictions can threaten revenues or

Notes: Values are sums of H100 equivalents from AI Supercomputers dataset (Pilz et al., 2025). Includes Existing and Planned installations as of 2025.

Figure 1: Distribution of Compute Power for High-End AI (Pilz et al., 2025)

slow global scaling for these actors. Similarly, smaller and middle states retain agency in bipolar cloud networks through strategic hub selection and segmentation (Lehdonvirta, Wu, and Hawkins 2025). By hosting multiple cloud providers, separating sensitive and non-sensitive workloads, and sequencing procurement commitments across domains, Gulf states can partially compartmentalize their technological dependencies. This does not eliminate structural constraints, but it allows states to distribute risk across ecosystems and delay full alignment. Therefore, while the AI infrastructure gravitates toward US-governed compute arrangements, this may not lead to a grand foreign policy posture.

Overall, compute's excludability and rivalrous character tie AI infrastructure to external compliance demands, especially from the United States and China. As AI supply chains become more securitized in the global AI race, infrastructure decisions increasingly carry geopolitical consequences, making broad hedging harder to sustain for middle powers and small states. For Gulf states, this means access to high-value compute increasingly comes bundled with security and compliance conditions, even if limited room for maneuver remains through segmentation, firms, and multi-cloud strategies. ♦

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